

Organic matter of buried soils as a carbon depot

Kovaleva N., Sidorova I., Kovalev I.

Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia, natalia_kovaleva@mail.ru

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Buried soils are an undervalued repository of carbon, a witness to the composition of the atmosphere at different time points in the evolution of the biosphere. The aim of the study was to assess the deposit potential of soils buried under archaeological monuments of historical time in the forest-steppe zone. The most humus soils - chernozems - are widespread in this zone.

The objects of the study are located in the central part of Hussian Plain - in the Tambov and Voronezh regions. The buried soils are confined to the Kozlovsky, Urlyapov and Ostrogozhsky ramparts of the Belgorod defensive line. On the mentioned ramparts there are chronocatenas of soils consisting of daytime chernozems on the top of the rampart and in the surrounding landscape, buried chernozems - under the ramparts and meadow-chernozem soils - in the bottom of the defensive ditches.

The research methods included determination of carbon on a CNS analyzer, determination of the isotopic composition of organic carbon on an isotope analyzer, radiocarbon dating of buried soil horizons, and determination of the rate of mineralization of organic matter using the substrate-induced respiration method.

The highest content of organic carbon in the soils of the ramparts is observed in the upper horizon on the rampart itself (about 4 %), approximately the same amount of carbon is in the buried chernozem. Increased carbon content is also characteristic of the cultural layers (2 %). In the background section, this indicator is 2 times less (1.82 %) than on the rampart, as a result of dehumification due to plowing. The enrichment of humus with nitrogen is low and very low (C / N - 12-15). The humus reserves in the surface horizons (100-200 t/ha) are less than those in the buried humus horizons in the body of the ramparts (200-300 t/ha) and are comparable to those in the chernozems buried under the ramparts (140 t/ha).

The dynamics of C-CO₂ formation with a maximum at the beginning of incubation and a gradual slowdown over time indicates a heterogeneous composition of the soil organic matter of buried soils, in which components protected from decomposition predominate. The content of active (potentially mineralizable) organic matter decreases exponentially down the profile, coinciding with the distribution of organic carbon. The organic matter of different soil horizons differs in mineralization rate constants. Most of the parameters characterizing the mineralization potential of soil organic matter (daily and cumulative production of C-CO₂, mineralization intensity, content of potentially mineralizable carbon) decreased in soils from the upper to the lower horizons, and their maximum values were observed in the chernozem-meadow soil.

The results of the carbon isotope analysis show that both the surface and buried soils were formed under the canopy of C-3 vegetation, since the range of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values is within -25.74 to -23.97 ‰ and corresponds to the woody vegetation of the temperate zone. At the same time, the surface horizons demonstrate the lightest values of isotope ratios: from -26.13 to -25.32 ‰. In the chernozems buried under ramparts, the values of isotope ratios are heavier to -23.97 ‰, which indicates episodes of a warm dry climate, apparently accompanied by a decrease in the groundwater level. The radiocarbon age of the chernozem buried under the ramparts is 2510±50 years, and the lower part of the AB horizon on the Tambov Plain was formed in the middle Holocene 6760±90 years ago.

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